

ELECTRONIC DICTIONARIES AS A NEW STAGE OF LEXICOGRAPHY

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Abstract. *The article talks about the role of computers in the development of the field of lexicography. The emergence of computer lexicography, the opinions of scientists about this field are presented. Advantages and disadvantages of electronic dictionary for users are highlighted. New types of dictionaries that appeared within the framework of computer lexicography are listed.*

Keywords: *lexicography, electronic dictionaries, automatic dictionary, lexical base, online dictionary, learner.*

INTRODUCTION

The intervention of the computer in science caused a radical change in lexicography. The capabilities of the computer began to solve the tasks and problems that a professional lexicographer can solve quickly and without spending a lot of money.

LITERATURE AND METHODS

Creating a dictionary in world linguistics has a long history. Jackson Harvard [1] connects the development of the science of lexicography with the establishment of the International Journal of Lexicography, which was founded in 1988. This magazine was aimed at covering issues related to the introduction of electronic dictionaries into lexicography. Therefore, we can connect the development of lexicography with the electronicization of this field.

N. Abdurahmanova recognized that this science is a field that studies the tasks of creating computer dictionaries and linguistic resources for software. Z. Kholmonova said that computer lexicography is an important component of applied linguistics, it is a field dealing with computer dictionaries working on the basis of software and linguistic knowledge, their creation and creation of programs, and development of algorithms. In addition to the above considerations, computer lexicography is a database of words in the lexicon of a specific language and the creation of programs (computer dictionaries) with an operating system using special programming languages, as well as learning a specific subject through a computer. It can be said that it is a teaching field. Of course, the goals, tasks and problems of the new lexicography are based on the sources of traditional lexicography. That is, it does not build dictionaries from scratch.

The creation of electronic dictionaries, considered the greatest achievement of new lexicography, is becoming more and more popular. An electronic dictionary is a type of dictionary designed to work on a computer or other electronic device that collects basic concepts related to the lexical system of the language or a specific field of knowledge and uses them automatically for intellectual purposes. In a general sense, an electronic dictionary refers to online or offline dictionaries with a search engine.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In a traditional dictionary, comments reflecting the structural composition of one or another word are provided, in accordance with the principles of creating an electronic dictionary, a program provided for users in a special computer format or as a component of a specific program

is provided. At the same time, according to how the user uses it, it differs from an electronic dictionary and an automatic dictionary for a word processing program [2]. Electronic dictionaries have the following options:

1. Ease of use;
2. Ownership of search engine;
3. The ability to regularly update the linguistic support;
4. Data transfer feature (via hyperlink);
5. Ability to directly integrate electronic dictionaries with other dictionaries;
6. Use in online and offline format;
7. Ability to provide orthographic information of the word.

Ease of use. Electronic dictionaries of use convenience that is, paper in the publication one how many from the part consists of, large voluminous, thousands the words reflection made whole head the dictionary one from the place two to the place take go to class in the process use possible it's not. For example, from 5 books consists of "Uzbek of the language explanatory dictionary" (2008) contains 80 thousand more than word and expressions collected. Speak up with work in the process users this from the dictionary efficient use they can't.

Ownership of search engine. Alphabet in order the word search of the user a lot the time takes Electronic in dictionaries the word alphabet in order not a graph and vocal pursuit function there is. Searched for unity again easy found get for searched for word dictionary in memory is stored.

The ability to regularly update the linguistic support. We know that language is a phenomenon of regular development and movement. The lexical base of the language is updated every day. Some words enter the language, some fall out of use. It is these processes that affect the content of dictionaries. In this case, frequent publication of a dictionary leads to expenditure of money and waste of paper. The ability to regularly update the word base of electronic dictionaries can be a solution to such problems.

Data transfer feature (via hyperlink). Most of the users use dictionaries to get accurate, scientific information about words. Using this information, they prepare articles, textbooks, lectures, etc. In such cases, you can copy the dictionary in electronic format or copy it to someone. As a result, there was a solution to all the problems in manually typing information about a word. Ability to directly integrate electronic dictionaries with other dictionaries. This feature of the electronic dictionary comes in handy when the user needs academic information about the word. For example, in the Oxford online dictionary you will see that several dictionaries have been combined.

Such an opportunity allows the user to combine all the meanings given about the word in several dictionaries, as well as to compare them. That is, the word's etymology, explanation, relationship with other words, spelling, pronunciation, morphemic composition, grammatical category, and similar information are useful for analyzing and synthesizing.

Ability to provide orthographic information of the word. While traditional dictionaries provide phonological aspects of words through accent and transcription, electronic dictionaries provide voice information. This feature is available in translation dictionaries for second language learners.

Experts point out a number of achievements of electronic dictionaries as well as their shortcomings. The faster and easier the information is found in the electronic dictionary, the faster it leaves the user's memory. This can cause the user to rely on the dictionary.

Currently, the following functional aspects should be taken into account when creating electronic dictionaries in our lexicography:

- simple and intuitive interface;
- the possibility of enriching words in the linguistic supply;
- quick search;
- voice search;
- in search spelling mistakes correction ;
- create the possibility of quick review of the list;
- adjust the font size in the list;
- consideration of the Latin and Cyrillic alphabets for the Uzbek language.

In addition, it is necessary to offer the purchase of additional content in order to enrich the vocabulary of the dictionary and use its full potential. We need linguistic databases (electronic dictionaries) for data processing [3]/.

CONCLUSION

It should also be mentioned that as a result of the development of this field, new concepts: electronic dictionary, online dictionary, automatic dictionary, associative dictionary, thesaurus dictionary, ontology, etc. . The listed dictionaries, of course, differ in their structure, features, and have their own tasks. Dictionaries are primarily designed to help users create, understand, or translate text and to provide specific cultural, encyclopedic, or linguistic knowledge. This means that dictionaries are not only for using the language, but also help to get various information.

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